

CONCEPT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: this article deals with what pedagogical technologies are currently being used in the educational system, namely the concept of pedagogical technology, and is explained through examples.

Keywords: pedagogical technology, UNESCO, B.Blum, D.Kratvol, N.Gronlund, J.Carroll, J.Block, L.Anderson.

Currently, the phrases “new pedagogical technology”, “advanced pedagogical technology”, “modern pedagogical technology” are widely used in pedagogical literature, lectures on educational problems, official documents. According to the definition of UNESCO: “pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining knowledge, taking into account the resources of the technical and individual and their interaction, which sets itself the task of effective forms of education in the process of teaching and mastering knowledge as a whole.” A key concept in this definition is “systematic style”. It is the systematic approach that is the main character that distinguishes pedagogical technology from other approaches to teaching. Educational goals, its content, teaching and teaching methods, control and design of outcome assessments in interaction and in connection with each other-are often what is lacking in the traditional learning process. For example, in many cases, education is mainly focused on remembering information, while the future activities of the learner are divided between doing certain things or making organizational, managerial and professional decisions. Pedagogical technology can be viewed as a referral, supposedly a mold, which determines certain general standards for the use of various teaching methods during the realization of the educational process. Through the term “technology”, a set of methods for changing the State, shape, property, properties of materials or semi-raw materials for conversion into finished products is understood, and it refers to the field of material production. Therefore, is it possible to “technologize” the educational activities of an educator belonging to the intellectual sphere? it is natural to question. “Our pedagogical production-wrote A.S.Makarenko, - never built on technological logic, he is always based on moral taribib. It is for this reason that we do not have the concepts of all important departments of production: accounting for the process of technology, the performance of work, creative (design) work, application of objects, control, commissioning, disposal to the unfit”. In the industry, thousands of technological processes have been developed that accurately comply with the requirements of technical documentation and give a guaranteed result without being in the person of the performer. The basis of such a technological process is served by a working drawing of detail and a drawing of prefabricated units. This is why the quality of the car produced in Uzbekistan on the basis of foreign technology does not differ from the quality of the car produced in South Korea. The creation of a repeating structure in

pedagogy is hampered by the variety of educational (educational) tasks, the variety of fragments of educational content and types of educational material, the uneven manifestation of the style of their cognitive activity, and many other factors. So, well-known scientists in the USA B.Blum, D.Kratvol, N.Gronlund, J.Carroll, J.Block, L.With the movement of Anderson et al, a pedagogical technology has been developed that includes a repetitive pedagogical structure that guarantees the achievement of planned results.

The flow of pedagogical technology that arose in the United States in the 70s and 80s spread to almost all developed countries, was recognized and applied by UNESCO, and is now successfully mastered in most countries. American pedagogy brought to the fore the demonstration of such a set of behaviors as knowledge, skills, thinking, assessment, behavior acquired in the educational process.

For example:

- to find at least 90 percent accuracy by reading the deliberately allowed error in the text;
- students perform behato actions over ten three-room issues;
- the reader describes how the animals adapt to their environment;
- surgically detects the internal organs of the Frog. It is necessary to note the specificity and accuracy of the above goals, the same specific goals are lacking in our educational system. 1) compare examples, fill empty spaces with words whose meaning is similar.

Life examples examples from the field of Education:

1. To get a good harvest, the tree is always _____ necessary. ↔ 1. Tireless to be educated _____ necessary.
2. _____ no bird can't fly ↔ 2. _____ no student can not learn
3. To hit the target _____ is taken to. ↔ 3. To learn _____ it is necessary to concentrate.
4. Bird egg _____ care with. ↔ 4. Teacher _____ when taught with, the student learns.

2) determine compatibility: (sample: 1-A, 2-E, 3-F, 4-C, 5-B, 6-G, 7-H, 8-D)

Processes in tree care processes in education 1. Water supply 2. Step 3. Checking the taste of the fruit 4. Rest in winter 5. Taking care within its term under the established rules 6. The application of the latest achievements in the industry 7. 8. Leveling the tree by cutting off branches. Base softening A. Organization of training according to plan B. giving students a break, a vacation C. giving knowledge D. E. improving knowledge by giving complex issues. Knowledge assessment F. positive stimulation G. the use of new pedagogical technologies H. discipline control

Answer: 1-__, 2-__, 3-__, 4-__, 5-__, 6-__, 7-__, 8-__.

3) Find and write down similar processes in the educational system: processes in bakeries processes in the Educational System 1. 2. Check the quality of flour, milk, butter-oil, various additives to take Improving the skills of workers 3. Determination of unwanted components in bread 4. 5. Knead the dough thing the dough 6. Baking bread 7. Production of new types of Bakery Products 8. Update, repair of enterprise equipment 9. Checking if the product meets the standard requirements 10. Product shipment to the consumer. 4) Fill out the boxes by writing suitable processes in the various areas indicated: control of students' knowledge when using a personal car in the production of food products in the construction of a building

in the educational system to give students knowledge, teach break and vacation planning the result of teaching on didactic principles – acquired knowledge.

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